

EVALUATION, HARVESTING AND MANAGEMENT OF FLUCTUATING STOCKS

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Abstract

Empirical data show that fish stocks fluctuate considerably and also sustain changes over periods of decades without a commercial fishery. These fluctuations are affected by environmental anomalies and by a fishery.

Single-species population dynamics approaches and maximum sustainable yield (MSY) concepts are no longer sufficient for evaluation and management of fishery resources; holistic ecosystem simulations are coming into use.

The "natural" fluctuations of the stock biomasses have periods of 4 to 7 years and magnitudes of 35% to 80% of equilibrium biomasses. To cope with such fluctuations, stocks should be managed on an annual basis. Increased efforts and accuracy of resource surveys are also required.

The main technological problems of fisheries caused by fluctuating stocks are: 1) increased flexibility in fishing fleets (multipurpose vessels and gear); 2) flexibility in processing and marketing; and 3) more effective utilization of discards (bycatch).

1. Introduction

Most fisheries resources, desirable for man at present, are heavily exploited. The abundance of some of these resources has declined and it has been assumed that overfishing has been the universal cause for these declines. Not much attention has been paid to the fact that there are pronounced natural fluctuations of the stocks, which appear as declines and inclines of abundance.

This paper summarizes the essential parameters of stock fluctuations and the implications of the fluctuations on fishery and its management.

2. Empirical Evidence on the Fluctuations of Fish Stocks and the Plausible Causes of These Fluctuations.

Some evidence of the short-term fluctuations of fish stocks is well presented with data on landings from local fisheries, where the improved search methods and the possibilities for spatial extension of fishery do not mask the fluctuating stock availability. Two examples of such fluctuations with periods of 4 to 8 years are given in Figures 1 and 2. Figure 2 shows a characteristic of the fluctuations of stocks: the higher the stock abundance, the greater is the magnitude of

fluctuations.

Quasi-periodic fluctuations of recruitment are usually more pronounced than fluctuations in landings. Jones and Hislop (1978) pointed out that, although North Sea haddock year-class strengths varied 3 orders of magnitude, its biomass varied only one order of magnitude and the catch per unit effort varied only maximum 1:5.

Figure 1.--Catch of young and adolescent Norwegian herring in 1930-1974 (from Dragesund et al., 1980)

Figure 2.--Total international landings of North Sea sole (after De Veen, 1978).

Some of the causes for fluctuations of stock biomasses are summarized in Table 1. Several

factors causing the changes in the biomasses can act simultaneously and with different intensity; therefore, the fluctuations are expected to be quite irregular.

Table 1.--External and internal factors causing fluctuations in marine ecosystem.

<u>Factors</u>	<u>Effects</u>
<u>External</u>	
Temperature anomalies	Affecting growth rate and food uptake, (thus predation rate).
Fishing	Removing older biomass, thus affecting predation, cannibalism, recruitment, and senescent mortality.
<u>Internal</u>	
Predation including cannibalism	Affecting recruitment to exploitable biomass; main mechanism in interspecies interaction in predator-prey system.
Competition	Can also affect starvation, which in turn affects growth.
Migration	Affecting predator-prey system by changing predator-prey overlap (local density) and prey availability.

Fishery will, obviously, affect the stock abundance and fluctuations, and fishery on one target species also affects the abundance of other, non-target species through interspecies interactions (mainly predation). The management and full utilization of fluctuating fisheries resources cannot be effected on the basis of the concept of MSY alone as this concept does not consider fluctuations nor interspecies interactions (Larkin, 1977). The fluctuating fish stocks should be managed on annual basis. The management requires accurate knowledge of the state (abundance) of the resource and its response to fishery.

3. Resource Surveys, Single-Species, and Ecosystem Approaches.

Resource survey, using a variety of techniques, is one of the main empirical methods for the evaluation of marine fishery resources; it will remain so despite its shortcomings such as high cost. However, several technological developments are desirable to improve the survey gear and methods, specially for capturing prefishery juveniles. Furthermore, there is an urgent need to determine catchability coefficient in various conditions.

The acoustic surveys are used for the survey of pelagic and semipelagic species. These surveys also have many shortcomings: calibration is often uncertain; frequent sampling is required to know which species (and which size) is acoustically recorded; coverage of area is narrow; and, due to possible fast migrations of species, synopticity of surveys are required. The main improvement of these surveys would come from a properly designed pelagic sampling gear, which can be rapidly deployed for sampling.

Virtual population analysis has been extensively used, especially in International Council for the

Exploration of the Sea (ICES) areas, for the estimation of the exploitable stock abundance. This method requires rather extensive sampling of commercial catch and good estimates of natural mortality. The latter is nearly unknown in most cases and only roughly guessed at. It is furthermore assumed in this method that fishery remains consistent in areas and times, and covers the distribution of whole stock. These requirements are seldom fully met.

Other single-species population dynamics approaches, used in the past, treat a species as if the other species do not exist and interact with each other (e.g., via predation). Furthermore, no environmental effects, recruitment variations, etc. can be used with these methods. The yield and biomass of gadids in the North Sea increased considerably in 1960's and 1970's (Figure 3) despite the fact that these species were considered "overfished" in the 1950's. No single-species approach predicted nor explained the increase. Several explanations have been offered for this phenomenon. However, it convinced most fisheries scientists and managers that neither single-species approaches nor MSY are satisfactory in research and management of fisheries, and that multispecies and/or holistic ecosystem approaches must be developed and applied in the future.

Figure 3.--Stock biomass and yield of cod, saithe, haddock, and whiting in the North Sea from 1960 to 1976 (Ursin, 1979).

Multispecies ecosystem simulations rectify some of the shortcomings of single-species approaches. Furthermore, the ecosystem approaches can compliment resource surveys. The first realistic multispecies model was that of Andersen and Ursin (1977), which is number-based model and is an extension of Beverton and Holt theory of fishing. It can be used for regions where the fisheries data are plentiful, such as in the North Sea. The Northwest and Alaska Fisheries Center (NWAFC) has developed a holistic dynamic ecosystem approach which is biomass-based (Laevastu and Larkins 1981). A comparison of single-species versus ecosystem approach for fisheries resource evaluation is given in Table 2. A simplified scheme of computations

Table 2.--Information for fisheries management and its availability from single-species population dynamics and ecosystem approaches.

Type of information needed	Availability from:	
	Single-species approach	Ecosystem approach
Size of the resource (stock)	Estimation with cohort analyses if data available	Equilibrium biomass computed; less stringent data requirements
Natural fluctuations	Not available	Computed, including the effects of environmental anomalies
Response to fishery	Computed for target species, no interspecies interactions included	Computed for all species, fishing and natural mortality interactions and effects on nontarget species incl.
Interactions between species	Not included	Included into the computations via predation, competition, bycatch
Possible optimum yield	Computed without interspecies interactions	Computed with consideration of whole ecosystem
Rate of change of biomass and recovery rates	Only rate of change due to fishery computed	Computed as caused by all factors within ecosystem
Recruitment to fishery	Can only be estimated	Computed, function of predation, env. anomalies and other factors
Spatial distribution and vulnerability to gear	Not possible to compute	Computed in models with spatial resolution

of primary processes and state variables is given in Figure 4.

Besides determination of the equilibrium biomasses, the ecosystem simulations are used for the determination of the response of the ecosystem to fishery, including the response to management options, and response of the ecosystem to environmental anomalies.

An example of the computed fluctuations of Pacific cod biomass in the Bristol Bay region is shown in Figure 5, together with the fluctuations of predation (consumption of cod). A summary of the data from simulated fluctuations is given in Table 3. The computed periods and magnitudes of the fluctuations are well comparable to those indicated in empirical data (Figures 1 and 2).

An example of the effect of temperature anomaly on the fluctuations of pollock biomass is given in Figure 6. The temperature anomaly affects both the magnitude and period of the fluctuations. The temperature anomaly effect on predominantly predator species (e.g. cod) is different from the effect on predominantly prey species (e.g. herring) due to the change of predation. Furthermore, the temperature effects vary from one region to another, depending on the acclimatization temperature of the local stocks. An example of the effect of fishery is shown in Figure 7, where pollock catch is doubled. The result is lowered biomass and decreased magnitudes of fluctuations of pollock.

4. Implications of Stock Fluctuations on the Fishery and its Management

When the resource availability fluctuates, the fishery should be able to switch from one species to another to remain fully occupied. The decrease of one stock of heavily harvested species can lead to increase in the abundance of less desirable species, which could, nevertheless, be harvested. A recent, rather pronounced example is the crab

Figure 4.--Simplified scheme of computation of processes and state variables in ecosystem simulation.

fishery in the eastern Bering Sea, which has been expanding rapidly, using very specialized gear and vessels. This crab fishery has changed emphasis from one species of crab to another. In 1981/82, most crab resources declined rapidly. It has not been possible to engage the specialized fleet in other fisheries without expensive rebuilding. Thus,

Table 3.--Some typical annual rates of changes of biomass (with reference to mean equilibrium biomasses, B_e) and typical periods and magnitudes of fluctuations of biomasses. Note: Percent of fluctuation computed as $\frac{B_1 - B_2}{B_e} \times 100$, where B_e is equilibrium biomass.

Species/ ecological group	Annual change (in % of B_e)		Fluctuations	
	Range	Mean	Mean period, years	Mean magni- tude (in % of B_e)
Flatfishes	7.5 to 13	10.5	6 to 7	45
Noncomm. demersal	8 to 26	12	5	40
Cod	7 to 20	13	7	35
Pollock	11 to 24	19	5	75
Herring	20 to 50	38	5	80
Squids	35 to 70	50	4	100
Benthos	65 to 80	75	4	120

Figure 5.--Fluctuations of Pacific cod biomass in Region 1 (Bristol Bay) in the Bering Sea and the consumption of cod biomass (in % of B_e).

in the future, developing fisheries have to consider multi-purpose vessels and gear to achieve flexibility.

Fluctuating stocks require flexibility also in processing and marketing of marine fish. Some of the products should be "interchangeable" on the markets to overcome user resistance to new products.

The discards vary normally between 30% and 50% of catches, but can reach as high as eight times the landings in the Gulf of Mexico shrimp fishery. The utilization of discards raise several problems such as space on vessels and processing. Experience has indicated that small processing plants located near ports of landing are a cost effective means for processing discards. Some under-utilized species in U.S. waters (e.g. hake, pollock) and some discards might be marketable if processed cheaply (e.g. salted, dried, etc.). The designing of cost effective processing plants

Figure 6.--Changes of pollock biomass with time in Region 2 in normal conditions and with temperature anomaly in years 1 to 3 (-1.5; -2.5; -1.5°C, respectively).

Figure 7.--Changes of pollock biomass with time in Region 2 in normal conditions and with doubled catches of pollock.

presents a challenge to technology.

The main objectives of fisheries management are: to obtain highest possible yield from a given resource and to guard the "health" of the ecosystem.

Successful fisheries management requires the following knowledge: a) magnitude (state) of the resource; b) fluctuations of the resource caused by environmental factors (including the magnitudes of fluctuations and rates of change); c) amounts which can be taken without undesirable effects on the stock (and on the ecosystem at large); d) other peculiarities of the resource (reproduction and recruitment potential, migrations, etc.); and e) response of the resource (and whole ecosystem) to fishery (and to management options).

Fisheries management may be considered a cooperative undertaking by its nature--the scientists presenting the state of the resource and the response of the ecosystem to management options, and the industry and populus at large (through representatives) making the decision which management options to select, considering economic, social, and ecosystem factors.

Pronounced fluctuations of the stocks require that the fisheries must be managed on an annual basis. A stock at the low level of its fluctuation cycle cannot be fished as heavily as it was fished at high levels of abundance, as "stock collapse" due to recruitment overfishing can occur. Stocks at low age but at high density give greatest yield. As the single-species concept is no longer sufficient to meet fisheries management problems, we must use ecosystem simulations for this purpose, which are supported and validated with good resource surveys. Ecosystem simulations also allow rapid testing of management options, presenting the changes which occur in the ecosystem with time.

5. Conclusions and Suggestions for Future Action

1. Catches of different species (and stocks) have fluctuated in the past. These fluctuations have been caused not only by fishery, but also by natural causes.

2. Reasons for stock fluctuations are: environmental anomalies, fishery, and ecosystem internal factors, mostly related to predation.

3. Resource surveys remain the main empirical means for assessment of the fishery resources. Resource surveys are expensive and need improvement: faster and better survey gear; gear for pre-fishery juveniles; and determination of catchability factors for different species. Acoustic methods also need to be improved: improved calibration methods and small, fast gear for sampling are required.

4. Single-species fisheries dynamics approaches are not sufficient for fisheries research and management. We need to add holistic ecosystem simulations for this purpose, which include all biota and environment and all pertinent knowledge and survey data.

5. Holistic ecosystem models are capable of producing equilibrium biomasses as well as natural fluctuations in the ecosystem which are caused by environmental anomalies. These models are also used for the study of management options.

6. Fluctuating stocks and accurate forecasts to industry require fisheries management on an annual basis.

7. Fluctuating stocks require flexibility in harvesting, processing, and marketing of fishery products.

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